

ISic3014

I.Sicily inscription 3014

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari, Antiquarium di
Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331257

1. [. Κορν]ήλιος Μαγουλι-
2. ανός
3. [ἱεροφ]άντης Ἐκάτης
4. [Σωτεί]ρης, ἄγος ὀσί-
5. ως
6. [έπετέλε]σεν ἰδίοις
7. [συνμ]ύσταις.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645362
EDCS 70901005
PHI 331257

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 34.0989
undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1966.0525
Manganaro, G. 1965. Per la storia dei culti in Sicilia. *Parola del Passato*. 20: 163-178. At 177
Spigo, U. 2005. Tindari. L'area archeologica e l'antiquarium. Messina. At 77
Manganaro, G. 2009. Divinità femminili nell'area peloritana e siracusana e l'emergenza di italici nella sicilia tardo ellenistica. *Sicilia Antiqua*. 6: 111-116. At 111 dr
Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 57 no.2 fig.20

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3014. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387965>